

ENTREPRENEDEU

Enhancing entrepreneurial ecosystems for education

HACKATHON'S IMPLEMENTATION REPORT

12/07/2024

Grant Agreement No.: 101100507
 Call: HORIZON-EIE-2022-SCALEUP-01
 Topic: HORIZON-EIE-2022-SCALEUP-01-01
 Type of action: HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions

D3.2 HACKATHON'S IMPLEMENTATION REPORT

HACKATHON ORGANIZER'S HANDBOOK AND PARTICIPANTS HANDBOOK TEMPLATE

Work package	WP3
Task	T3.4
Due date	October 2024
Submission date	12/07/2024
Deliverable lead	Athena / Corallia
Version	1.0
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Abstract	This deliverable refers to the implementation and management of the three competitions - hackathons organized by the ENTREPRENEDU team. Held across Italy, Greece, and Bulgaria, these competitions aimed to foster innovation and entrepreneurship in "low/moderate-innovation countries." The deliverable outlines the collaborative efforts of Fondazione E. Amaldi, Corallia, and Cleantech Bulgaria in ensuring a diverse range of ideas and solutions. Under the leadership of Corallia, all three hackathons were delivered successfully.
Keywords	Hackathon, HackTheBusiness, Hackathon Handbook, entrepreneurship, innovation, mentorship

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributors(s)
0.1	5/2/2024	Table of Contents shared	Corallia
0.2	6/3/2024	First draft ready	Corallia
0.3	26/4/2024	Second draft ready	Corallia
0.4	17/05/2024	Collection of feedback by partners	Corallia, FEA, F6S, Cleantech
0.5	31/05/2024	Deliverable and Annex ready for internal review	Corallia
0.6	21/6/2024	Final adjustments	Corallia
0.7	5/7/2024	Deliverable ready for submission	Corallia
1.0	12/7/2024	Deliverable submitted	Corallia

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2	FRAUNHOFER	FhG IPK	DE
3	EUROPEAN BUSINESS ANGELS NETWORK	EBAN	BE
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

During the implementation of the ENTREPRENEDU project, 3 hackathons have been organized in 3 different locations in relatively low/moderate-innovation countries: Italy, Greece and Bulgaria. This distribution guaranteed the diversification of participants, stakeholders, industries, sectors involved, and solutions generated. The partners responsible for supervising the hackathons were: Fondazione E. Amaldi, Corallia and Cleantech Bulgaria.

To ensure alignment between the three ENTREPRENEDU hackathons, Corallia, with its consolidated experience in designing, promoting, organizing these events, and ensuring contextualization at the European, national, and regional level, led the overall coordination. To facilitate this coordination across the different locations, an overall framework and specific guidelines were established.

This deliverable is the outcome of such a coordination activity, focusing on the actual implementation and management of the three hackathons organized by the ENTREPRENEDU partners. In the next sections, an analysis of the activities that took place from June 2023 to March 2024 follows. During these months, Corallia has guided the ENTREPRENEDU partners in delivering 3 successful hackathons.

This report is structured as follows: Subsequently to this summary, chapter 1 introduces the HackTheBusiness concept, and provides an overview on the structure and organization of the three consecutive hackathons, chapter 2 presents the first HackTheBusiness, organized by Fondazione E. Amaldi which took place in Italy, chapter 3 focuses on the Greek hackathon organized by Corallia and chapter 4 covers the final Hackathon in Bulgaria, organized by Cleantech Bulgaria. Lastly, chapter 5 concludes this report.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

KPI	Key Performance Indicator
Q&A	Questions and Answers

1 INTRODUCTION

The general objective of the ENTREPRENEDU project is to create a highly replicable and scalable venture building program, an educational model for the European entrepreneurial ecosystems developed via a series of 3 Hackathons, developed at regional level, supporting concepts and ideas to become concrete solutions.

1.1 ABOUT HACKTHEBUSINESS

This section introduces the ENTREPRENEDU Hackathon Competition and its objectives. Further, the structure and particular characteristics of each hackathon competition are analyzed.

HackTheBusiness has been an entrepreneurship challenge for young minds to learn, explore and discover the secrets of the DeepTech industry. The competition encouraged participants to think outside the box, refine their pitches, and leverage their creativity. HackTheBusiness event has been the perfect opportunity for young individuals and startups to present their business concepts to a panel of esteemed judges and industry leaders and get invited to the ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring & Coaching Programme, where they could receive all the support needed to level-up their business idea.

Though the format of each Hackathon varied to better fit the context, seize local opportunities, better involve local multipliers and stakeholders and address participants, all three hackathons were based on a common structure, consisting of the four main stages described below.

FIGURE 1 THE STAGES OF THE ENTREPRENEDU HACKATHON

1.2 TARGET GROUP

HackTheBusiness targeted students, new startups, and researchers interested in acquiring entrepreneurial skills and exploring their business potential. Participants were challenged to propose revolutionary business ideas that could lead to successful start-ups.

Teams of 1-6 members.
EU residents 18-40 old.

FIGURE 2 TARGET GROUP

The competitions were open to EU residents aged 18-40 and primarily intended for on-site participation. Contestants could compete individually or in teams of up to six members.

Registrations took place through an online platform provided by the communication leader, F6S, and was available through the project website (an extract of the registration form is available in the annex). Participants could register individually or as pre-established teams, indicating their skills to help balance team profiles. Aiming for gender diversity, the organizers selected up to 80 participants for the hackathon. Ineligible applicants were still encouraged to participate virtually by following keynotes, workshops streamed live on social media during the event's key moments, and the final pitch session with awards.

1.3 EVENT LOGISTICS

Participation in all hackathons was free of charge.

Full meals were provided for the duration of the competition.

Participants were free to bring their own devices (chargers, power strip, etc.) with Wi-Fi capability. The organizers provided the credentials for free internet resources for the duration of the event.

The premises were open to the participants throughout the duration of the event. The participants had to accept the terms and conditions of use of the facilities.

1.4 BENEFITS FROM THE COMPETITION

Through the participation in the competition, participants gained access to the following opportunities:

- **Networking opportunities** – The competitions have brought together passionate and talented people from various fields and expertise. By attending the event, participants had the opportunity to connect with other professionals, industry experts and potential collaborators.
- **Professional growth** – The competitions have offered a stimulating and collaborative environment where participants acquired new skills, refine their expertise, and learned from experienced mentors and other participants.
- **Visibility and recognition** – By participating in the competitions and presenting innovative solutions, participants had the opportunity to gain visibility and recognition. This could lead to further opportunities for collaboration with organizations taking part in the competition.
- **Interdisciplinary skills** – The competitions offered the opportunity to work with people from different disciplines, learning to collaborate and integrate ideas and knowledge to create more comprehensive and innovative solutions.
- **Mentoring** – Throughout the competitions, participants had the chance to attend workshops and receive 1-to-1 mentoring from experts in the field. All mentors have provided support, resources, and guidance to participants to turn their ideas and projects developed during the event into successful businesses.

1.5 TEAMS PRESENTATION

All teams had to submit a presentation (PowerPoint or PDF) by the set deadline. A template was provided that outlined further details on the content to be included in the presentation. A demonstration/technical implementation related to the final presentation was optional. The template is available in the annex.

The presentation included the following:

- **The Introduction:** A summary of what you are going to present. Open with a simple statement such as “This is our team, and this is what we do.”
- **The Problem:** Description of the problem that you try to remedy or the opportunity that you try to take advantage of. Avoid looking for a solution that is searching for a problem.
- **The Solution:** Explain how you resolve the problem and the value that you create. It is not necessary to provide an in-depth technical explanation. Provide just the gist of how you fix the problem (but do make sure that your idea is feasible).
- **The Market:** Explain who are the customers/consumers you target. Quantify the market (e.g., How big is it, in monetary terms?).
- **The Business/Pricing model:** Explain how you can make money—who pays you, what are the channels of distribution you are going to use, what are your gross margins, etc.

- The Competition: Are there alternatives? Are there direct or indirect competitors? Briefly categorise them.
- The Unique Selling Point(s): Describe what makes you different from the competition.
- The Team: Present your team-members' skills and roles. Identify why you are the team to solve the problem.
- The Timeplan: What are the next steps you can take to implement your idea? Are there any milestones?
- The Financials: Present the expected costs, required funding you would need to make your idea a reality, and your expected revenues (projections/estimations).

Beyond the presentation submission, the teams had to pitch their idea and present it within a specific time-limit in front of a jury. Following the pitching session, the jury members could ask questions to the participants.

1.6 EVALUATION CRITERIA

The evaluation criteria were:

- **Technical Innovation:** Is the idea innovative? Does it rely on Technology Transfer? Does it have the potential to secure Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs)?
- **Market Attractiveness:** Does the idea address a real problem? Is there a market for it?
- **Business Viability:** Is the business model sound? Can a company built around the presented idea run a successful business?
- **Investors Interest:** Overall, can the idea attract interest from potential investors?
- **Funding Opportunities:** Does the idea have the potential to secure funding from other sources (beyond investors), such as grants?
- **Educational Impact:** Does the business/idea have a (side-)effect on the education sector? Can people be trained/educated through it?
- **Team Quality:** Is this the Team to solve the Problem?
- **Branding & Marketing:** Has the team worked on its values, its branding, and its marketing (e.g., name selection for business/product, logo creation, graphics, creative content, etc.).

Evaluation (1 = Does not address the criterion at all; 10 = Fully addresses the criterion)

#	Project	Technical Innovation	Market Attractiveness	Business Viability	Investors Interest	Funding Opportunities	Educational Impact	Team Quality	Branding & Marketing
1	TEAM 1								
2	TEAM 2								
3	TEAM 3								
4	TEAM 4								
5	TEAM 5								
6	TEAM 6								
7	TEAM 7								
8	TEAM 8								
9	TEAM 9								
10	TEAM 10								
11	TEAM 11								

FIGURE 3 EVALUATION TEMPLATE

1.7 DISSEMINATION

F6S, the communication leader, prepared the whole branding material for all three events including the communication kit, press releases, posts, landing page, registration tool, flyers, badges etc. In addition, 5 warm-up sessions were organized by the ENTREPRENEDU partners in cooperation with F6S as part of the pre-hackathon campaign in order to disseminate the events and attract participants.

Notably, F6S created dedicated webpages for each competition, serving as central hubs for vital information such as competition details, agendas, and registration portals. This streamlined approach facilitated seamless navigation for participants, enhancing their overall experience and fostering greater interaction with the event.

FIGURE 4 HACKTHEBUSINESS - WEBSITE

More information is available for each hackathon in sections 2, 3 and 4.

1.8 PERSONAL DATA

ENTREPRENEDU obtained the necessary ethics approvals and obtained the free and fully informed consent of the participants of all three hackathons. Target participants were entirely voluntary, and ENTREPRENEDU obtained and clearly documented participants' informed consent in advance. All participants received a project-specific informed consent form (see Annex) and detailed information sheets that:

- were written in a language and terms they could fully understand.
- described the aims, methods, and implications of the project activity, the nature of participation, and any benefits, risks, or discomfort that might ensue.
- explicitly stated that participation was voluntary and that anyone had the right to refuse to participate and to withdraw their participation or data at any time – without any consequences.

The template of the authorization form is included in the Annex.

ENTREPRENEDU ensured that potential participants fully understood the information and did not feel pressured or coerced into giving consent. ENTREPRENEDU partners ensured informed consent by providing and explaining the consent form and information sheets that participants were required to sign.

1.9 MONITORING

Corallia was responsible for the overall management of the three hackathons organized by the ENTREPRENEDU team. To ensure effective coordination, seamless communication, and

KPIs	INDICATOR	TARGET	ACTUAL	HACK-ITALY	HACK-GREECE	HACK-BULGARIA
Applications	Nr.	n/a	212	43	108	61
Business Ideas	Nr.	90	94	30	35	29
Teams (Individuals)	Nr.	90 (30/Hackathon)	41 (111)	11 (20)	18 (68)	12 (23)
Finalists	Nr.	12 teams in total	13	4	4	5
Workshops during the Hackathon	Nr.	4-6/Hackathon	16	6	5	5
Pitching session	Nr.	1/Hackathon	8	1	6	1

In reference to the indicators, the following provides an explanation of each:

- **Applications:** Counts the total registrations per competition.
- **Business Ideas:** Considers the number of teams, startups, and individuals through the F6S page who indicated having a business idea.
- **Teams:** Considers the number of teams and startups that took part in the competition,
- **Finalists:** Represents the number of winning teams per competition.
- **Workshops during the Hackathon:** Counts the number of workshops that took place during the events.
- **Pitching Sessions:** Refers to the pitches delivered by participants during each competition.

2 HACKTHEBUSINESS ITALY

FIGURE 6 HACKTHEBUSINESS ITALY LOGO

HackTheBusiness Italy took place in **Rimini** during the “We Make Future 2023” event (**15-17 June 2023**), the largest digital innovation fair in Italy, where a dedicated space was reserved for hacking, workshops, and pitches, an ideal occasion to organize the HackTheBusiness competition.

We Make Future has become synonymous with innovation, technology, and entrepreneurial spirit. This prestigious event attracts forward-thinking individuals from various industries, offering a unique

opportunity to explore emerging trends, network with industry experts, and gain invaluable insights.

HackTheBusiness Italy counted a total of **43 applications with 30 business ideas**. The aim of the hackathon was to bring together young talents and new entrepreneurs who are passionate or have an interest in Deeptech with experts of business and innovation to work together and develop innovative solutions enabled by Deeptech to address the needs of industry and society.

Fondazione E. Amaldi was responsible for organising all aspects of the Italian hackathon, from logistics to strategic stakeholder engagement, challenge definition, development of the guide for participants and Evaluation Board management.

FIGURE 7 HACKTHEBUSINESS ITALY, NEWSLETTER BANNER

2.1 THE HACKATHON CHALLENGE

FIGURE 8 HACKTHEBUSINESS ITALY, BRANDING

Participants were invited to propose Deeptech business ideas that represent a real revolution for the food, climate, and space sectors.

The description of the challenges is given below.

Challenge SPACE: This challenge sought business ideas that leveraged satellite data and space technologies to solve problems across various industries (energy, transportation, agriculture, etc.) The focus was on using space data and AI to analyze large datasets and create innovative solutions. It also highlighted the need for innovation in the space sector itself, such as new satellites and components. The aim of this challenge was to propose a business idea that addressed one or

more of the issues that characterize the space sector.

Challenge FOOD: This challenge was about business ideas that used new technologies (AI, Blockchain, IoT) to create a more sustainable food system. The goal was to address issues like food security, reducing environmental impact from farming, and minimizing resource waste.

Challenge CLIMATE: This challenge searched for ideas that utilized emerging technologies to mitigate and adapt to climate change. Examples included intelligent forecasting systems, monitoring carbon neutrality, planning renewable energy grids, and protecting people from extreme weather events.

2.2 PRIOR TO THE COMPETITION

2.2.1 COMMUNICATION CAMPAIGN AND PROMO MATERIAL

ENTREPRENEDU partners collaborated to broaden the events' visibility and outreach by leveraging their extensive reach and expertise. F6S, the communication leader, has provided the event platform (<https://www.f6s.com/entreprenedu-hackthebusinessitaly>) to the Hackathons which was managed by the core organizer (Fondazione Amaldi). The platform included all the information required for potential participants to learn about the basics of the competition. It also included the corresponding registration form.

An extract of the registration form can be found at the Annex.

Furthermore, F6S developed a comprehensive set of promotional and dissemination materials to maximize engagement. These materials included dynamic content tailored to different platforms (LinkedIn, Facebook, and YouTube) and audiences, ensuring widespread awareness

and participation. Additionally, F6S published a press release about the competition on the ENTREPRENEDU website (see Annex).

FIGURE 9 HACKTHEBUSINESS ITALY, SAMPLE OF COMMUNICATION MATERIALS

FIGURE 10 HACKTHEBUSINESS ITALY, LINKEDIN POSTS

2.2.2 HANDBOOK – GUIDE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Prior to the competition, Fondazione E. Amaldi prepared a comprehensive handbook for participants, available to be downloaded from the website. This handbook contained valuable information, such as the event’s timeline, agenda, eligibility criteria, stakeholder information, prizes, and other helpful details necessary for successful participation in the competition.

FIGURE 11 HACKTHEBUSINESS ITALY, PARTICIPANTS HANDBOOK

2.2.3 WARM-UP SESSIONS

Fondazione Amaldi, with the support of FS6, organized a warm-up session on May 30, 2023, as part of the pre-hackathon campaign in order to disseminate the events and attract participants (registration page available at <https://www.f6s.com/hackthebusiness-italy-webinar>). The session drew 28 attendees. Since then, the video recording has been viewed 45 times (data as of June 7, 2024).

Recording of the session is available on the project digital channels at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DdV6QOCUbw5>

FIGURE 12 HACKTHEBUSINESS ITALY, WEBINAR

During this session, participants had the opportunity to virtually meet the organizing team, ask questions, and delve into the intricacies of the competition. The event proved highly successful, offering all attendees a deep dive into the ENTREPRENEDU world.

2.2.4 COMMUNITY PARTNERS

The community partners of the HackTheBusiness Italy were the following:

- [Hypatia Research Consortium](#)
- [Teseas](#)
- [Fondazione Piemonte Innova](#)
- [Polo di Innovazione ICT](#)
- [Search On Media Group](#)

FIGURE 13 HACKTHEBUSINESS ITALY, COMMUNITY PARTNERS

2.3 THE COMPETITION

Over the three days of the competition, participants collaborated intensively with mentors to finalize their business ideas and leave a positive impression on the judges and audiences. The pressure was high as each team aimed to deliver a concise and persuasive pitch highlighting their vision, value proposition, and market potential. To support their DeepTech development, participants had also the opportunity to attend workshops led by ENTREPRENEDU experts, gaining valuable business insights and practical tips.

FIGURE 14 HACKTHEBUSINESS ITALY, HACK TIME

2.3.1 COMPETITION TIMELINE

2.3.2 AGENDA

TIME	ACTIVITIES
DAY 1 - THURSDAY 15TH JUNE	
09:30 – 16:00	WELCOME AND REGISTRATION PARTICIPANTS ARRIVE AT THE VENUE & MINGLE.
15:00 - 16:00	LAUNCH SESSION - HACKATHON KICK-OFF AND TOPICS PRESENTATION WELCOME FROM THE LOCAL ORGANIZERS AND IMPORTANT INFORMATION. PARTICIPANTS/TEAMS INTRODUCTION. [16:00-16:30] INTRODUCTION LORENZO SCATENA, SECRETARY GENERAL - FONDAZIONE E. AMALDI [16:55-17:20] PRESENTATION OF ENTREPRENEDU'S HACKTHEBUSINESS FORMAT ELEONORA LOMBARDI, HEAD OF BUSINESS APPLICATIONS DPT. - FONDAZIONE E. AMALDI [16:30-16:55] PRESENTATION OF THE CHALLENGES/TOPICS AND LOGISTICS VALERIO ROSCANI, TECHNOLOGY ANALYST - FONDAZIONE E. AMALDI [17:20-17:45] PRESENTATION OF THE ENTREPRENEDU MENTORING PROGRAMME HENRY NICOLAI BUXMANN, RESEARCHER - FRAUNHOFER IPK [17:45-18:00] CONCLUSION BY FEA AND INVITATION TO WELCOME DRINK ELEONORA LOMBARDI, HEAD OF BUSINESS APPLICATIONS DPT. - FONDAZIONE E. AMALDI
17:30 - 18:30	WELCOME DRINK
DAY 2 - FRIDAY 16TH JUNE	

09:00 - 09:15	WELCOME AND REGISTRATION PARTICIPANTS AND EXPERTS ARRIVE AT THE VENUE & MINGLE.
09:15 - 10:30	WORKSHOP SESSION [10:00-10:20] BUSINESS MODEL DISCOVERY KATRIN SINGER-COUDOUX, RESEARCHER AND PROJECT LEADER - FRAUNHOFER IPK
10:30 - 11:00	COFFEE BREAK
11:00 - 13:00	WORKSHOP SESSION [11:30-11:50] SPARK YOUR SUCCESS: UNLEASHING THE BRILLIANCE WITHIN YOUR IDEAS VERONICA SPADONI, HEAD OF BUSINESS UNIT "BUSINESS ACCELERATOR AND INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS AT FONDAZIONE PIEMONTE INNOVA – CLUSTER MANAGER AT ICT INNOVATION HUB
13:00 - 14:00	NETWORKING LUNCH
14:00 - 16:00	WORKSHOP SESSION [14:30-14:50] BUILDING FUTUREPROOFED BUSINESS IDEAS ACHILLEAS BARLAS, NATIONAL COORDINATOR OF EEN HELLAS AND ADJUNCT LECTURER - UTH. [15:30-15:50] UNDERSTANDING BUSINESS ANGELS - FUNDRAISING TIPS FOR STARTUP FOUNDERS JACOPO LOSSO, DIRECTOR GENERAL - EBAN
16:00 - 16:30	COFFEE BREAK
16:30 - 18:00	WORKSHOP SESSION [17:30-17:50] FROM IDEA TO IMPACT: UNLOCKING THE POTENTIAL OF YOUR BUSINESS CONCEPTS INA TODOROVA, PROJECT COORDINATOR - CLEANTECH BULGARIA
DAY 3 - SATURDAY 17TH JUNE	
09:00 - 09:15	"WELCOME AND REGISTRATION PARTICIPANTS AND EXPERTS ARRIVE AT THE VENUE & MINGLE."
09:15 - 11:00	"WORKSHOP SESSION [09:30-09:50] ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN SPACE LORENZO SCATENA, SECRETARY GENERAL - FONDAZIONE E. AMALDI WORKSHOP SESSION [10:00-10:20] HOW TO APPLY TO EUROPEAN SPACE AGENCY BUSINESS INCUBATION CENTERS JORGE-A. SANCHEZ-P., CO-FOUNDER AND CHIEF STRATEGY & FINANCIAL OFFICER - CORALLIA [10:30-10:50] USEFUL TOOL FOR DEEPTECH BUSINESS IN EUROPE, ESA BUSINESS APPLICATIONS PLATFORM ESA"
11:00 - 12:00	COFFEE BREAK
12:00	ENTREPRENEDEDU PITCH SUBMISSION DEADLINE
12:00 - 12:30	FEEDBACK COLLECTION
13:00 - 14:00	NETWORKING LUNCH
14:00 - 15:00	FEEDBACK COLLECTION
15:00 - 15:30	NETWORKING LUNCH
15:30 - 16:30	FEEDBACK COLLECTION
16:30 - 17:00	"AWARD CEREMONY OF THE PITCH COMPETITION @PRIMAVERA DELL'INNOVAZIONE ALL LOCAL WINNERS ARE ANNOUNCED, AND THE HACKATHON WRAP UP/ THANK YOU."

2.3.3 WORKSHOPS

Throughout the competition, the ENTREPRENEDU team delivered six training workshops. These workshops provided participants with in-depth knowledge and analysis on developing entrepreneurial ecosystems tailored to regional innovation levels and specific needs.

The topics covered are presented in the following table:

	Session	Facilitator
1	BUILDING FUTUREPROOFED BUSINESS IDEAS	Achilleas Barlas - UTH
2	UNDERSTANDING BUSINESS ANGELS - FUNDRAISING TIPS FOR STARTUP FOUNDERS	Jacopo Losso - EBAN
3	BUSINESS MODEL DISCOVERY	Katrin Singer-Coudoux - Fraunhofer IPK
4	FROM IDEA TO IMPACT: UNLOCKING THE POTENTIAL OF YOUR BUSINESS CONCEPTS	Ina Todorova - Cleantech Bulgaria
5	ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN SPACE	Lorenzo Scatena - FEA
6	HOW TO APPLY TO EUROPEAN SPACE AGENCY BUSINESS INCUBATION CENTERS	Jorge-A. Sanchez-P. - Corallia

2.4 WINNING TEAMS

After three days of intense work, excitement, learning, and fun, the ENTREPRENEDU team of experts selected the top four winning teams and their innovative DeepTech ideas. The winning teams were: BACKWARDS, SHADES OF BLUE, AS YOU LIKE, and BOBIS.

BACKWARDS team is eager to solve the problem of packaging waste by creating reusable packaging and logistics infrastructure!

SHADES OF BLUE team wishes to create a certification system and consultancy services for sustainable management of water resources, providing companies monitoring, improving, and communicating the negative impact on rivers and water.

AS YOU LIKE team aims to transform the dining experience with a mobile app: customize meals, access real-time nutrition info with Visual-AI, and discover restaurants aligned with dietary needs.

BOBIS team has a goal to reduce CO2 emissions caused by last mile logistics, offering the end user a platform that can encourage local consumption and the search for products and services within 3km.

FIGURE 15 HACKTHEBUSINESS ITALY, WINNERS 2023

FIGURE 16 HACKTHEBUSINESS ITALY, BACKWARDS-1ST PLACE

2.5 PRIZES

The main prize for the 4 winning teams was:

- Access to the exclusive 60-hour ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring & Coaching Programme

Other prizes offered by the sponsors were:

- Tickets for the New Space Economy Expo forum offered by Fondazione E. Amaldi
- Tickets for the Maker Faire Rome offered by Fondazione E. Amaldi
- AWS Activate Programme offered by European Business Angels Network

2.6 USER SATISFACTION

To continuously improve future Hackathons, the consortium gathered feedback from teams, startups, other participants, and project partners who attended the event in Rimini, Italy. After submitting their final projects on June 17th, participants were invited by the Fraunhofer IPK team to scan QR codes and complete a satisfaction survey. Teams and startups could choose to have one member complete the survey or allow all members to participate individually.

Overall, the respondents were satisfied or very satisfied with the ENTREPRENEDU Hackathon overall. Moreover, they found the challenges relevant or very relevant and all five workshops were assessed by the majority of respondents as very relevant or highly relevant. Thus, the Hackathon was well-received, offering relevant challenges and valuable workshops. The consortium partners also provided positive feedback, recognizing the event's success, and suggesting enhancements for the future. Mentorship support was praised, though improvements were suggested for participant engagement. In total, 12 measures for future improvement for all partners were derived, concerning the topics "Promotion & Website information", "Application Process", "Workshop topics", "Mentoring & Collaboration", and "Hackathon structure & planning". A detailed analysis of the feedback and a detailed deviation of improvement measures can be found in the "Feedback Collection" (Deliverable 4.3).

The HackTheBusiness Italy competition fostered connections and collaborations by providing an ideal environment for networking with like-minded individuals, potential investors, industry influencers, and representatives from renowned organizations. This valuable aspect allowed participants to build relationships, explore partnership opportunities, gain exposure to a broader innovation ecosystem, and ultimately experience professional growth.

3 HACKTHEBUSINESS GREECE

FIGURE 17 HACKTHEBUSINESS GREECE, LOGO

The second HackTheBusiness competition organized by the ENTREPRENEDU team was held in Greece in November 2024, where emerging talents gathered to showcase their groundbreaking space-ideas.

HackTheBusiness Greece was the first entrepreneurship and educational Ideation Contest that took place on a national level. The aim was to bring together young entrepreneurs with business and innovation experts to work together and develop

innovative solutions enabled by Deeptech to address the needs of industry and society.

The HackTheBusiness Greece competition was organized by Corallia, with the support of the European Space Agency Business Incubation Centre Greece ([ESA BIC Greece](#)), the Greek Space Technologies and Applications Cluster ([si-Cluster](#)), the [STARTAB](#) Entrepreneurship Programme and was under the Aegis of the Ministry of Digital Governance with four co-organizers the National Technical University of Athens, the University of Thessaly, the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki and the Democritus University of Thrace.

HackTheBusiness Greece consisted of two phases. During the First Phase, four different local competitions (physical events) took place simultaneously in different cities all over Greece in collaboration with local Universities (Athens, Thessaloniki, Volos, Xanthi). During the Second Phase (Final), winners of each local competition gathered in Athens, where they pitched their ideas against each other.

HackTheBusiness Greece counted a total of 108 applications with 35 business ideas.

Corallia as the main organizer was responsible for all related activities (logistics, strategic stakeholders, and sponsors engagement, challenges definition, development of several guides -local organizers, jury, participants- Evaluation Board management).

FIGURE 18 HACKTHEBUSINESS GREECE, EXTRACT FROM THE WEBISTE

3.1 THE HACKATHON CHALLENGE

FIGURE 19 HACKTHEBUSINESS GREECE, BRANDING

The main Theme of the competition was “Space”. More specifically, participants were invited to:

- identify a problem/challenge faced by the space industry and provide a solution based on pre-existing or new space technology and/or systems.
- introduce a product or service based on a transfer of space technology to, and/or the utilisation of, a space system in a non-space environment (spin-off). For example, the participants could suggest the usage of images from Earth Observation satellites to create a new precision agriculture application.
- introduce the exploitation of non-space technology in the space market (spin-in). For instance, the participants could suggest the introduction of blockchain technology (originally coming from the logistics/financial sector) into the management of satellite clusters.

In other words, if “space” was the source of the challenge to be faced and/or the source of the solution to be provided, any innovative idea was acceptable.

FIGURE 20 POTENTIAL SPACE TECHNOLOGIES AND APPLICATION AREAS

3.2 PRIOR TO THE COMPETITION

3.2.1 COMMUNICATION CAMPAIGN AND PROMO MATERIAL

F6S has provided the event platform to the Hackathon (<https://www.f6s.com/entrepreneuru-hackthebusinessgreece>) which was managed by the core organizer (Corallia). The platform included all the information required for potential participants to learn about the basics of the competition and the corresponding registration form. F6S prepared the branding materials for the overall promotion and dissemination of the event and has supported the necessary communication actions for the Greek hackathon.

An extract of the registration form can be found at the Annex.

FIGURE 21 HACKTHEBUSINESS GREECE, BRANDING MATERIALS

F6S has also designed the event materials, which included customized designs for notebooks, tote bags, pens, stickers, and badges for each phase of the competition.

In addition, Corallia together with the four local organizers and the ENTREPRENEDU partners ran their own dissemination campaigns (social media, press releases, articles, newsletters etc.) to attract participants. Some examples are presented below.

FIGURE 22 HACKTHEBUSINESS GREECE, PARTICIPANTS KIT

FIGURE 23 HACKTHEBUSINESS GREECE, SAMPLE FROM PUBLIC ARTICLES

FIGURE 24 HACKTHEBUSINESS GREECE, SAMPLE FROM SOCIAL MEDIA POSTS

3.2.2 HANDBOOKS – GUIDE FOR PARTICIPANTS

Different handbooks for each competition phase and target group (local organizers, participants, stakeholders, potential community partners/sponsors) were prepared and distributed (in total 6 handbooks). These handbooks provided comprehensive information about the HackTheBusiness Greece, including details on organization, preparation, event logistics, prizes, and other resources for a successful and beneficial experience.

FIGURE 25 HACKTHEBUSINESS GREECE, PARTICIPANTS HANDBOOK, AUTH

FIGURE 26 HACKTHEBUSINESS GREECE, PARTICIPANTS HANDBOOK, FINALS

3.2.3 WARM-UP SESSIONS

Corallia, with the support of F6S, successfully organized 3 warm-up sessions with a total of 79 participants. Since then, the video recordings of the warm-ups have been viewed 60 times (data as of June 7, 2024).

Each warm-up session's theme and date are stated below:

	Warm-up session	Date
1	The Greek Space Ecosystem	18/10/2023
2	Success stories from Greek Space Start-ups	25/10/2023
3	Competition Hints & Tips	1/11/2023

The goal of each session was to not only attract potential participants, but also to train them and provide highlights of the market and the technologies related to the space sector. Overall, the sessions offered participants invaluable information, expert tips, and profound insights in preparation for the upcoming competitions.

FIGURE 27 HACKTHEBUSINESS GREECE, WARM-UP SESSIONS

Following each event, engaging Q&A sessions facilitated networking opportunities and allowed participants to ask questions and seek clarifications. Additionally, winners of previous hackathons shared their inspiring stories on how they transformed ideas into successful startups. Lastly, keynote speeches on the space ecosystem enriched the experience, offering strategic perspectives and fostering a deeper understanding of the industry landscape.

All three warm-up sessions (available at <https://www.youtube.com/@entreprenedu>) have had a significant impact on promoting the event and attracting participants from across Greece. During these sessions, participants were introduced to the concept of the hackathon and encouraged to form teams with fellow members.

The Zoom platform was utilized to facilitate the warm-up sessions.

FIGURE 28 HACKTHEBUSINESS GREECE, WARM-UP SESSIONS

3.2.4 COORDINATION WITH LOCAL ORGANIZERS (EDUCATIONAL ENTITIES)

Educational entities (Democritus University of Thrace, National Technical University of Athens, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, University of Thessaly) have played a crucial role in the organization of the first phase of the HackTheBusiness Greece, acting as local organizers. This enabled universities to reinforce their position as hubs of education and innovation, engage with their local ecosystems, and identify new space challenges and solutions. The competition also served as a milestone linked to future activities, further solidifying their involvement in the Greek space sector.

From September to October 2023, Corallia hosted six biweekly coordination calls with the educational entities to ensure the smooth operation of the organization. Corallia provided the local organizers with the entire framework and documentation related to the educational, technical, and competitive part of the event. Such material included:

- Competition Rules
- Competition Framework (evaluation criteria)
- Terms & Conditions
- Participants playbook
- Educational Scientific and Business material

Through a common repository, Corallia has shared with all local organizers the brand kit (visual identity and graphical guidelines, templates, logos pack, images, etc.) and marketing materials (templates for teaser text, newsletters, social media posts, etc.), to enable them to run their own promotional activities. Promotional items with the unique branding of the competition were provided to all local organizers so that they could be distributed to the contestants.

Local Organizer's responsibilities included the following activities:

- joining (bi-) weekly coordination calls
- event planning and preparation
- ensuring communication with the central hub
- local judging, video recording, and taking photos and interviews
- setting up the local infrastructure
- engaging local facilitators and experts
- involving relevant partners from the local ecosystem

Local organizers were also responsible for securing an appropriate venue for the event. At the very least, the venue should cover the following requirements:

- enough capacity (for organizers, participants, mentors, judges, etc.)
- appropriate space arrangement (locations for attendees to compete and listen to speakers, as well as allocated sections for equipment, food, sponsors, breaks, etc.)
- enough chairs and desks/tables, at the proper setup
- fast, secure, and dependable Wi-Fi
- enough power to support tenths of laptops and phones
- AV resources and personnel (at the very least, a projector)
- lavatories and janitorial services
- air conditioning and heating
- Security and Accessibility

3.2.5 COMMUNITY PARTNERS

The community partners of the HackTheBusiness Greece were the following:

- [ASAT](#), Aristotle Space & Aeronautics Team
- [BEAM AUTH](#), Beyond Earth Aristotle Missions
- [Consortis](#), Engineering Consultants
- [GEO University](#)
- [GEOSYSTEMS HELLAS](#)
- [Innovation and Entrepreneurship Unit](#) of University of Thessaly (IEU-UTH).
- [Microsoft Learn](#)
- NTUA Laboratories: The [Remote Sensing Laboratory](#) and the [Microprocessors and Digital Systems Lab](#).

- [OHB Hellas](#)
- [Planetek Hellas](#)
- [Research Committee of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki](#)
- [Thinc Thrace incubator](#), Democritus University of Thrace.
- [Walk AUTH Innovation Accelerator](#) and [SpaceDot Team](#), on behalf of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH).
- [IEEE](#), Aristotle University Student Branch

FIGURE 29 SPONSORS AND COMMUNITY PARTNERS

3.3 THE COMPETITION

The first phase of the event was organized from 03 to 05 November 2023 at 4 different Universities, across Greece: Democritus University of Thrace (DUTH); National Technical University of Athens (NTUA); Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH); University of Thessaly (UTH). Teams with the most innovative ideas received mentoring and a paid ticket to the finals. The second phase of the competition - the finals, took place in Athens, Greece on 25 November 2023 at Corallia premises.

The HackTheBusiness Greece competition was a hybrid event. The first phase featured physical events in four locations, with workshops and one-on-one mentoring sessions conducted both

online (discord used) and physically. The final event and awards ceremony included on-site participation from both organizers, participants, and speakers.

FIGURE 30 HACKTHEBUSINESS GREECE, ORGANIZERS

3.3.1 COMPETITION TIMELINE

The timeline of the competition follows.

FIGURE 31 HACKTHEBUSINESS GREECE TIMELINE

3.3.2 PHASE ONE

FIGURE 32 HACKTHEBUSINESS GREECE, LOCATION MAP

In the First Phase, 4 different local competitions (physical events) took place simultaneously in 4 different cities in Greece in collaboration with the Educational Entities, under the coordinated guidance of Corallia.

Participation to the local competition (3-5 November 2023) consisted of the following steps:

- Registration to the local competition (until the 2nd of November).
- On-site registration/confirmation on the first day of the competition (3rd of November).
- Participation in the Launch Session of HackTheBusiness (3rd of November).
- Team finalisation (for participants finding a team

on-site).

- Working with your team and asking for support from the local organizers and experts (4th of November).
- Pitch submission and presentation to the jury (5th of November).
- Feedback collection on user satisfaction.
- Participation in the Award Ceremony and learn if you've won!

During the three-day local competitions, participants actively collaborated with mentors to refine their business ideas and captivate the judges. Teams attended four workshops led by the ENTREPRENEDU team and sponsors, gaining valuable business insights. Furthermore, one-to-one sessions were organized between the hackathon teams and the mentors. These sessions focused on both technical and business aspects of the solutions, as well as on presentation hints and tips.

The award ceremony was live-streamed across all four locations in Greece, with winners selected by local organizers in collaboration with Corallia.

In the first phase of the competition, a total of 68 participants, divided into 18 teams, participated.

During the local competition, all official communications were conducted through the Discord platform. Discord was utilized to connect mentors with participants and for teams to submit their project ideas. Streaming of events (e.g., Launch Session and webinars) also took place through this platform.

FIGURE 33 HACKTHEBUSINESS GREECE, COMMUNITY PLATFORM (DISCORD)

At the end, 10 teams emerged as winners. The 10 winning teams were the following:

- **UNIWA ICE team**, that uses satellite imagery and sensor data to identify and address factors affecting olive tree production.
- **MicrosatLab team**, that develops a system using Earth Observation data to monitor and manage aquatic resources, tackling issues like overfishing.
- **Groundwater team**, that leverages Earth Observation data analysis for efficient detection of potential groundwater locations for large-scale projects.
- **Luminous team**, that provides an AI platform that analyzes agricultural data to empower farmers with solutions for crop diseases and maximize yield.
- **Spa/c team**, that designs air conditioner filters based on space technology, aiming for affordability, eco-friendliness, and safety.
- **Ocean Defenders team**, that monitors and prevents marine plastic pollution by tracking plastic movement using Earth Observation data.
- **Exke team**, that develops a new solar sail to remove CubeSats from orbit, addressing limitations of existing deorbiting methods.
- **PPD Control team**, that creates DORA, an AI-powered solution for analyzing spacecraft health and suggesting maneuvers to mitigate operational risks.

- **KORI space team**, that offers an innovative ophthalmology solution potentially linked to space missions.
- **Prometheus Auth team**, that develops PEM fuel cells for space applications, aiming for higher efficiency, lifespan, and environmental sustainability.

Elevator pitch

Due to the high quality of participating teams in the first phase of the competition and in order to ensure that all locations will be represented, Corallia organized a second round of qualifying some additional pitches.

The challenge for the second round was to present an elevator pitch of approximately 8 minutes to a jury of Corallia members. The event was held online and was attended by the shortlisted teams from the first phase of the competition.

Following this, two more teams won a place in the finals in Athens, resulting in a total number of 12 teams.

The two winning teams of the elevator pitch were the following:

- **Home4you team**, that develops an application to help new residents find the best places to live based on environmental and social factors.
- **Dirnaut team**, that creates HPS (Hazards Prevented from the Sky), a solution to simulate, detect, monitor, and respond to environmental disasters.

All 12 winning teams from Phase 1 have received:

- Travel vouchers to visit Athens for the Finals (for those outside Athens).
- Special prizes, depending on the local organizers and sponsors of each competition.

FIGURE 34 HACKTHEBUSINESS GREECE, LOCAL COMPETITION (NTUA, DUTH)

FIGURE 35 HACKTHEBUSINESS GREECE, LOCAL COMPETITION, AUTH

3.3.2.1 AGENDA

Below you can find the agenda of the 1st phase.

Day 1 – Friday 3rd of November

TIME (EET)	ACTIVITY	DETAILS
16:00-17:00	WELCOME BY LOCAL ORGANIZERS AND REGISTRATION	PARTICIPANTS ARRIVAL, OFFICIAL ON-SITE REGISTRATIONS, LATE REGISTRATIONS, TEAMS' FORMATION.
17:00-18:30	LAUNCH SESSION - COMPETITION KICK-OFF (HYBRID)	WELCOME AND KEYNOTE SPEECHES. INTRODUCTORY PRESENTATION FROM CORE ORGANIZERS (ONLINE). PRESENTATION OF INSTRUCTIONS, RULES, AND THE FINAL AGENDA OF THE EVENT.
	17:00-17:15	INTRODUCTION BY CORALLIA AND OPENING REMARKS, DR. JORGE-A SANCHEZ-P, CO-FOUNDER & CSFO CORALLIA, DIRECTOR ESA BIC GREECE, CHAIRMAN SI-CLUSTER
	17:15-17:30	WELCOME BY THE GENERAL SECRETARY OF TELECOMMUNICATIONS & POST, PROF.K. KARANTZALOS
	17:30-18:00	WELCOME TO THE ENTREPRENEDU WORLD, MR. VALERIO ROSCANI, ENTREPRENEDU PROJECT MANAGER AND TECHNOLOGY ANALYST, FONDAZIONE E. AMALDI
	18:00-18:30	PRESENTATION OF THE HACKTHEBUSINESS FORMAT, MR. ORFEAS VOUTYRAS, SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY ASSOCIATE, CORALLIA
	18:30-19:00	CONCLUSIONS AND INVITATION TO A NETWORKING SESSION
19:00-20:00	NETWORKING SESSION	NETWORKING BETWEEN PARTICIPANTS, MENTORS, LOCAL ORGANIZERS. TEAMS' FORMATION.
20:00		CLOSURE OF THE FIRST DAY

Day 2 – Saturday 4th of November

TIME (EET)	ACTIVITY	DETAILS
09:00-10:00	ARRIVALS AND TEAMS FINALISATION	PARTICIPANTS ARRIVAL. OFFICIAL REGISTRATION OF THE TEAMS WITH THEIR FINALISED FORM
10:00-10:30	WORKSHOP SESSION	“BUSINESS MODEL DEVELOPMENT”, KATRIN SINGER-COUDOUX, FRAUNHOFER IPK
10:30-14:00	WORKING & MENTORING TIME	TEAMS WORKING ON THEIR IDEA AND THEIR PRESENTATION. 1-TO-1 MENTORING SESSIONS MAY TAKE PLACE IN PARALLEL SYNCHRONOUSLY / ASYNCHRONOUSLY
14:00-15:00	LUNCH & NETWORKING	
15:00-15:20	WORKSHOP SESSION	“SOLVING PROBLEMS ON EARTH WITH SATELITE E.O.” MR. STELIOS BOLANOS, CO-FOUNDER & DIRECTOR, PLANETEK HELLAS
15:20-16:00	WORKING & MENTORING TIME	TEAMS WORKING ON THEIR IDEA AND THEIR PRESENTATION. 1-TO-1 MENTORING SESSIONS MAY TAKE PLACE IN PARALLEL SYNCHRONOUSLY / ASYNCHRONOUSLY
16:00-16:30	WORKSHOP SESSION	“UNLOCKING THE POTENTIAL OF YOUR BUSINESS CONCEPT”, INA TODOROVA, CLEANTECH BULGARIA
16:30-17:00	WORKSHOP SESSION	“PITCHING TIPS”, YEORYIOS STAMBOULIS, UTH
17:00-19:00	WORKING & MENTORING TIME	TEAMS WORKING ON THEIR IDEA AND THEIR PRESENTATION. 1-TO-1 MENTORING SESSIONS MAY TAKE PLACE IN PARALLEL SYNCHRONOUSLY OR ASYNCHRONOUSLY.
19:00-20:00	NETWORKING	
20:30	CLOSURE OF THE SECOND DAY	

Day 3 – Sunday 5th of November

TIME (EET)	ACTIVITY	DETAILS
09:00-09:30	ARRIVALS	
09:30-14:00	WORKING & MENTORING TIME	TEAMS WORKING ON THEIR IDEA AND THEIR PRESENTATION. 1-TO-1 MENTORING SESSIONS MAY TAKE PLACE IN PARALLEL SYNCHRONOUSLY OR ASYNCHRONOUSLY
14:00	SUBMISSION DEADLINE	DEADLINE FOR THE SUBMISSION OF THE TEAMS’ PRESENTATION (.PPTX OR .PDF FORMAT)
14:15-14:45	LIGHT LUNCH	
15:15-17:15	PITCHING SESSION	THE TEAMS PRESENT THEIR IDEA TO THE JURY AND ANSWER TO THEIR QUESTIONS
17:15-18:00	BREAK	DELIBERATION BY THE JURY
18:00-19:00	CLOSING CEREMONY	ANNOUNCEMENT OF WINNERS AND AWARDS CEREMONY
19:30	CLOSURE OF THE THIRD DAY	

3.3.2 MENTORING BEFORE PHASE TWO

Winners of the local competitions were invited to join the mentoring program offered by the Corallia team. This program provided winning teams with the opportunity to receive guidance from experienced mentors, who helped them refine their business ideas, enhance their expertise, and excel in the competition.

In November 2023, 23 sessions were conducted with 12 teams. Each team had the opportunity to participate in up to two mentoring sessions before the final competition on November 25th.

3.3.3 PHASE TWO

Following local competitions, winners from each region gathered in Athens on November 25, 2023, to pitch their innovative business ideas for a chance to join ENTREPRENEDU's business acceleration program, where promising ventures could receive the support needed to become reality.

The final competition was held under the auspices of the Ministry of Digital Governance, with the Deputy Minister in attendance. Community partners and stakeholders actively joined the final competition and during the first part of the day, they shared their insights about space and entrepreneurship, while three successful startup companies, alumni of previous hackathons, shared their inspiring stories and their journey to become a successful entrepreneur.

FIGURE 36 HACKTHEBUSINESS GREECE, KEYNOTE SPEECHES

During the second part of the day, each team had a limited seven-minute window to articulate the vision and mission behind their space solutions. After each pitching session, the teams answered questions from the jury committee. Following all pitches, the 12 teams were evaluated based on the criteria specified in section 1.6, including innovation, feasibility, market scalability, and social impact.

The jury committee consisted of the following members:

- Mr. Valerio Roscani, FEA
- Prof. Federica Brunetta, LUISS University
- Mr. Henry Nicolai Buxmann, FRAUNHOFER
- Mr. Daniel Silva, F6S
- Mrs. Ina Todorova, CTBG
- Mr. Christos Kontopoulos, GeoSystems Hellas

The award ceremony followed with the announcement of the winners and prizes and the final event concluded with networking between all participants, partners, investors, and fellow attendees.

FIGURE 37 HACKTHEBUSINESS GREECE, FINALS, PITCHING SESSION

FIGURE 38 HACKTHEBUSINESS GREECE, GROUP PHOTO

3.3.3.1 AGENDA

Saturday, 25th of November

TIME (EET)	TOPIC	
10:00-11:00	WELCOME AND REGISTRATION	JURY MEETING
SALUTATION OF ORGANIZERS		
11:00-11:15	MRS. NEKTARIA BERIKOU & DR. ORFEAS VOUTYRAS, CORALLIA	
SALUTATION OF HELLENIC DEPUTY MINISTER OF DIGITAL GOVERNANCE		
11:15-11:30	MR. KONSTANTINOS KYRANAKIS, DEPUTY MINISTER, MINISTRY OF DIGITAL GOVERNANCE	

SALUTATION FROM THE LOCAL SPACE ECOSYSTEM		
11:30-11:35	DR. MANOLIS ZERVAKIS, EFA GROUP	
11:35-11:40	DR. IOSIF PARASKEVAS, IDE	
11:40-11:45	MR. EVGENIOS TSIGKANOS, OHB HELLAS	
11:45-11:50	MR. CHRISTOS KONTOPOULOS, GEOSYSTEMS HELLAS	
11:50-11:55	MR. STELIOS BOLANOS, PLANETEK HELLAS	
11:55-12:00	Q&A	
THE JOURNEY TO BECOME A SPACE ENTREPRENEUR		
12:00-12:20	DR. JORGE-A. SANCHEZ-P., CORALLIA	
12:20-12:30	DR. ANTONIS GOTSIS, INSIGH.IO	
12:30-12:40	MR. ATHANASIOS KOTSARAS, ANGELY	
12:40-12:50	MR. GEORGE MENDRINOS, CAIUS	
12:50-13:00	Q&A	
GROUP PHOTO & LUNCH BREAK		
PITCHING		
AWARDS CEREMONY & NETWORKING		
17:00-18:00	COFFEE BREAK	DELIBERATION BY THE JURY
18:00-19:30	AWARDS CEREMONY AND NETWORKING	

3.3.4 WORKSHOPS

Throughout the competition, the ENTREPRENEDU team, along with an event sponsor, delivered five training workshops. These workshops provided participants with in-depth knowledge and analysis on developing entrepreneurial ecosystems tailored to regional innovation levels and specific needs. The topics covered are presented in the following table:

	Session	Facilitator
1	BUSINESS MODEL DEVELOPMENT	Katrin Singer-Coudoux, Fraunhofer IPK
2	PITCHING TIPS	Yeoryios Stamboulis, UTH
3	UNLOCKING THE POTENTIAL OF YOUR BUSINESS CONCEPT	Ina Todorova, CleanTech
4	SOLVING PROBLEMS ON EARTH WITH SATELLITE E.O	Stelios Bolanos, Planetek
5	THE JOURNEY TO BECOME A SPACE ENTREPRENEUR	Jorge-A. Sanchez-P., Corallia

3.4 WINNING TEAMS

Demonstrating remarkable entrepreneurial spirit and passion, all participants showcased their ideas in the Finals of the HackTheBusiness Greece contest.

The 4 winning teams of the final competition were MicroSatLab, Exke, Uniwa-Ice and Groundwater.

MICROSATLAB team introduces Psarema, a precision system for aquatic resource monitoring and analysis based on earth observation to tackle problems such as overfishing and unregulated fishing.

UNIWA ICE team develops a solution based on data fusion of satellite imagery and IOT sensors data to identify, monitor, and mitigate the factors that reduce olive tree production levels.

EXKE team, presents a new solar sail to be provided as a solution for active deorbiting solution for cubesats tackling the challenges faced by other deorbit approaches.

GROUNDWATER team exploits earth observation data analysis for fast, automatic, and precise detection of candidate groundwater locations for large scale projects, leaving behind traditional in-situ detection techniques.

FIGURE 39 HACKTHEBUSINESS GREECE, AWARD CEREMONY, CORALLIA 2023

3.5 PRIZES

The 4 winning teams received:

- the exclusive ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring & Coaching Programme for business acceleration (60 hours of mentoring and strategic consulting from experts coming from 6 high innovation European entities, and networking with potential investors and businesses partners).
- a tailored support programme from ESA BIC Greece, the only Business Incubation Centre of the European Space Agency in the Balkans.
- €6,000 prize in vouchers that was shared between all teams.

All participants received:

- A certificate of participation to the event
- a 4-day intensive entrepreneurship course by STARTAB Programme.

FIGURE 40 HACKTHEBUSINESS GREECE, CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION TEMPLATE

3.6 USER SATISFACTION

To ensure continuous improvement of the Hackathons, a survey was distributed to participants who attended the Hackathon after the final competition's pitching session. Participants were invited to scan QR codes and complete a satisfaction survey. Teams and startups could choose to have one member complete the survey or allow all members to participate individually. The Hackathon was well-received, with participants finding it valuable and offering relevant challenges and valuable workshops.

Further, some potential customers and end-users were impressed with the quality of the presented ideas. The consortium partners also provided positive feedback, recognizing the event's success, and suggesting enhancements for the future. While the structure of the Hackathon process was praised, minor improvements were suggested for the mentoring process. A more detailed analysis and results of the feedback and a detailed deviation of improvement measures would be available on the "Feedback Collection" (Deliverable 4.6).

4 HACKTHEBUSINESS BULGARIA

HackTheBusiness HACKATHON **BULGARIA** 26 & 27 March, Sofia

FIGURE 41 HACKTHEBUSINESS BULGARIA, LOGO

This dynamic business ideation competition provided a space for aspiring entrepreneurs to harness their creativity, collaborate with like-minded individuals, and bring their innovative ideas to life. HackTheBusiness Bulgaria counted a total of 61 applications with 29 business ideas.

In a groundbreaking finale hosted by Cleantech Bulgaria, the third and final installment of the HackTheBusiness hackathon series sparked a wave of innovation set to redefine Europe's sustainable landscape.

Cleantech Bulgaria hosted the final round of the ENTREPRENEDU HackTheBusiness Bulgaria, an entrepreneurial hackathon for students, young professionals, and early-stage startups.

HackTheBusiness Bulgaria was a golden opportunity for aspiring European entrepreneurs to step into the business world. Participants were invited to delve into the realms of sustainability and digitization, addressing challenges from diverse sectors.

4.1 THE HACKATHON CHALLENGE

With a sharp focus on green and eco-conscious solutions spanning agri-food, construction, manufacturing, digital and creative industries, participants were primed to unleash their creativity and address pressing environmental challenges head-on. The goal was to catalyse contributions towards a future that's not only environmentally aware but also resilient across these pivotal sectors.

4.2 PRIOR TO THE COMPETITION

4.2.1 COMMUNICATION CAMPAIGN AND PROMO MATERIAL

F6S has provided the event platform (<https://www.f6s.com/entreprenedu-hackthebusinessbulgaria>) to the Hackathons, which were managed by the core organizer (Cleantech Bulgaria). The platform included all the information required for potential participants to learn about the basics of the competition. It also included the corresponding registration form. F6S has also prepared the branding materials for the overall promotion and

dissemination of the event and has supported the necessary communication actions for the Bulgarian hackathon. An extract of the registration form can be found at the Annex.

FIGURE 42 HACKTHEBUSINESS BULGARIA BRANDING MATERIAL

4.2.2 WARM-UP SESSION

Cleantech Bulgaria with the support of FS6, organized an info session on March 7th, 2024, as part of the pre-hackathon campaign in order to disseminate the event and attract participants. There were 18 registrations for the session and in total 9 participants joined the live session. Furthermore, the video recording has been viewed 90 times since then (data available on 07 June 2024).

FIGURE 43 HACKTHEBUSINESS BULGARIA, WEBINAR

4.2.3 COMMUNITY PARTNERS

Below is the list of community partners that contributed to the competition:

- [Fund of Funds](#)
- [Sofia Tech Park](#)
- [Ministry of Innovation and Growth](#)
- [Sofia University](#)

FIGURE 44 HACKTHEBUSINESS BULGARIA, COMMUNITY PARTNERS

4.3 THE COMPETITION

HackTheBusiness Bulgaria took place on March 26th and 27th at the Innovation Forum “John Atanasoff” of Sofia Tech Park, gathering young entrepreneurs, researchers, and early-stage startups to pitch innovative and sustainable business ideas. Hosted by Cleantech Bulgaria, this event aimed to transform the European sustainable ecosystem and received a variety of eco-conscious solutions and ideas connected with agri-food, construction, manufacturing, and digital and creative industries. Participants had the opportunity to network and gain valuable insights from mentors in the industry.

The HackTheBusiness Bulgaria competition was an onsite event. On the first day of the competition, participants had the opportunity to form teams, meet the mentors, and attend workshops carefully designed by the ENTREPRENEDU team to equip them with the necessary skills and knowledge to master their pitch decks.

FIGURE 45 HACKTHEBUSINESS BULGARIA, MENTORING

FIGURE 46 HACKTHEBUSINESS BULGARIA, WORKSHOP SESSIONS

During the second day of the competition, each team had a limited seven-minute window to articulate the vision and mission behind their solutions. After each pitching, the teams answered questions from the jury committee. Following all pitches, the 12 teams were evaluated based on the criteria specified in section 1.6, including innovation, feasibility, market scalability, and social impact.

The jury committee consisted of the following members:

- Mr. Achilleas Barlas, UTH
- Mr. Daniel Silva, F6S

- Prof. Federica Brunetta, LUISS University
- Mr. Henry Nicolai Buxmann, FRAUNHOFER
- Mrs. Ina Todorova, CTBG
- Mrs. Nektaria Berikou, Corallia
- Mr. Valerio Roscani, FEA

FIGURE 47 HACKTHEBUSINESS BULGARIA, EVALUATION COMMITTEE

The event concluded with an impressive award ceremony where the winners and prizes were announced. Following the award ceremony, a networking cocktail took place for all participants, partners, investors, political figures, and fellow attendees.

The Consortium partners decided to announce five winning teams instead of the originally planned four due to a withdrawal of one of the teams in cohort one of the ENTREPRENEDU Coaching and Mentoring Programme. The top five teams have already joined the ENTREPRENEDU project's Programme.

FIGURE 48 HACKTHEBUSINESS BULGARIA, KEY-NOTE SPEECHES

4.3.1 COMPETITION TIMELINE

4.3.2 AGENDA

TIME	ACTIVITIES
DAY 1 - TUESDAY 26TH MARCH	
09:00 - 09:30	WELCOME AND REGISTRATION PARTICIPANTS ARRIVE AT THE VENUE & MINGLE.
09:30 - 10:10	LAUNCH SESSION - HACKATHON KICK-OFF AND TOPICS PRESENTATION WELCOME FROM THE LOCAL ORGANIZERS AND IMPORTANT INFORMATION. PARTICIPANTS/TEAMS INTRODUCTION. [09:30-09:40] INTRODUCTION MARIYANA HAMANOVA, EXECUTIVE DIRECTOR - CLEANTECH BULGARIA [09:40-09:50] PRESENTATION OF ENTREPRENEDU PROJECT VALERIO ROSCANI, FEA [09:50-10:00] PRESENTATION OF ENTREPRENEDU'S HACKTHEBUSINESS FORMAT AND LOGISTICS INA TODOROVA, PROJECT COORDINATOR - CLEANTECH BULGARIA [10:00-10:10] PRESENTATION OF THE MAIN PRIZE: ENTREPRENEDU MENTORING PROGRAMME - HENRY NICOLAI BUXMANN, FRAUNHOFER IPK
10:10 - 10:40	WORKSHOP SESSION INTRODUCTION TO BUSINESS CREATION: YOUR PATH TO SUCCESS - INA TODOROVA, PROJECT COORDINATOR - CLEANTECH BULGARIA
10:40 - 11:30	HACKING TIME: SETTING THE GROUND
11:30 - 12:00	WORKSHOP SESSION BUSINESS MODEL DEVELOPMENT - KATRIN SINGER-COUDOUX, FRAUNHOFER IPK
12:00 - 13:00	NETWORKING LUNCH
13:00 - 16:00	HACKING TIME
16:00 - 16:30	COFFEE BREAK
16:30 - 17:30	HACKING TIME
17:30 - 17:50	WORKSHOP SESSION THE PERFECT PITCH - UNIVERSITY OF THESSALY
17:50 - 18:00	CONCLUSION OF DAY 1 AND INVITATION TO THE OFFICIAL COCKTAIL WITH THE LOCAL ECOSYSTEM INA TODOROVA, PROJECT COORDINATOR - CLEANTECH BULGARIA
18:00-20:00	OFFICIAL COCKTAIL AND THE OPENING OF THE "BEST YOUTH STARTUP IN BULGARIA 2024" INITIATIVE [18:00-18:05] MILENA STOYCHEVA, MINISTER OF INNOVATION AND GROWTH [18:05-18:10] BISER PETKOV, CHAIRPERSON OF THE MANAGING BOARD - FMFIB [18:10-18:15] ASS. PROF. ATANAS GEORGIEV – DEAN OF FACULTY OF ECONOMICS AND BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION - SOFIA UNIVERSITY "ST. KLIMENT OHRIDSKI" [18:15-18:20] DANIEL SILVA, PROJECT MANAGER - F6S [18:20-18:30] DOTCHKA VASSILEVA, HEAD OF PROJECT INFORMATION AND FINANCING UNIT – FMFIB [18:30-20:00] NETWORKING
DAY 2 - WEDNESDAY 27TH MARCH	
09:00 - 09:15	WELCOME AND REGISTRATION PARTICIPANTS AND EXPERTS ARRIVE AT THE VENUE & MINGLE.
09:15 - 09:45	WORKSHOP SESSION FROM IDEA TO CONTEXT: THE CORE BLOCKS OF STRATEGIC ANALYSIS - FEDERICA BRUNETTA, LUISS UNIVERSITY
09:45 - 13:00	HACKING TIME

13:00	PITCH SUBMISSION DEADLINE
13:00 - 14:00	NETWORKING LUNCH
14:00 - 15:00	FEEDBACK COLLECTION AND EVALUATION OF THE SUBMITTED PITCH DECKS
15:00 - 16:00	PITCHING SESSION FOR TOP 10 SELECTED TEAMS
16:00 - 16:30	COFFEE BREAK
16:00 - 16:30	FEEDBACK COLLECTION AND FINAL JURY DECISION MAKING PROCESS
17:00 - 18:00	AWARD CEREMONY OF THE PITCH COMPETITION ALL LOCAL WINNERS ARE ANNOUNCED, AND THE HACKATHON WRAP UP/THANK YOU!

4.3.3 WORKSHOPS

Throughout the competition, the ENTREPRENEDU team delivered six training workshops. These workshops provided participants with in-depth knowledge and analysis on developing entrepreneurial ecosystems tailored to regional innovation levels and specific needs.

The topics covered are presented in the following table:

	Session	Facilitator
1	INTRODUCTION OF THE PROJECT	Valerio Roscani, FEA
2	FROM IDEA TO CONTEXT: THE CORE BLOCKS OF STRATEGIC ANALYSIS	Federica Brunetta, LUISS
3	BUSINESS MODEL DEVELOPMENT	Ina Todorova, CleanTech
4	PITCHING TIPS	Henry Nicolai Buxmann, FRAUNHOFER
5	INTRODUCTION TO BUSINESS CREATION: YOUR PATH TO SUCCESS	Achilleas Barlas, UTH

4.4 WINNING TEAMS

After two days of hacking and learning, the ENTREPRENEDU team of experts selected the top five winning teams and their innovative sustainable ideas. The winning teams of the HackTheBusiness Competition were the followings.

LOCAL. team, - Marketplace for locally sourced goods through a network of verified producers

BRICK3D

Brick3D team - Brick3D is a 3D printing company that makes learning and using 3D printing technology accessible and fun for schools and individuals at home. They offer a range of products and services, including printable bricks, lesson plans, trainings and rental options, to help users get started with 3D printing.

AI School team - An online platform offering expert-created educational content that helps individuals acquire new skills, refine their expertise, or automate daily tasks using artificial intelligence.

Foodilizer team - Disrupting agriculture by providing a sustainable and efficient alternative to mineral fertilizers.

Green team - innovative solution to maintain and build a healthy sustainable relationship between the population and the environment, through a thriving local biodiversity.

FIGURE 49 HACKTHEBUSINESS BULGARIA AWARD CEREMONY, 2024

FIGURE 50 HACKTHEBUSINESS BULGARIA, WINNING TEAMS, 2024

4.5 PRIZES

The main prize for the 5 winning teams was:

- Access to the exclusive 60-hour ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring & Coaching Programme

Other prizes offered by the sponsors were:

- a certificate for participation in the hackathon HackTheBusiness Bulgaria
- discount deals on the F6S website, as well as offers for discounts and memberships from the European Business Angels Network.

FIGURE 51 HACKTHEBUSINESS BULGARIA, CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION TEMPLATE

4.6 USER SATISFACTION

Following the final pitches, participants were asked to share their feedback by scanning a QR code and completing a satisfaction survey. Participants found it valuable, with challenges that were relevant and workshops that provided useful knowledge. Participants were satisfied with the concepts they developed (prototypes, etc.) and saw the pitching session as a great opportunity to showcase their business ideas. There were also ample networking opportunities for everyone. Overall, all attendees had a positive experience. A detailed analysis of the feedback and a detailed deviation of improvement measures would be available on the “Feedback Collection” (Deliverable 4.6).

For aspiring young entrepreneurs, HackTheBusiness Bulgaria was the perfect springboard. They got to present their innovative and sustainable business ideas to a distinguished panel of judges. Winning teams have already started their journey to the ENTREPRENEDU Coaching and Mentoring program, where they'll receive all the necessary support to turn their ideas into reality.

5 CONCLUSION

ENTREPRENEDU's HackTheBusiness initiative culminated in a resounding success, fostering innovation, and supporting young people in Europe. Twelve winning teams, chosen from three hackathons held in Italy, Greece, and Bulgaria, have now embarked on the ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring & Coaching Programme. This targeted program equips young entrepreneurs with the essential knowledge and guidance to transform their innovative ideas into successful startups. The program's impact extends beyond the winners, as over 100 participants from across Europe actively participated in the hackathons. Participants showcased their creativity and technical prowess by developing solutions in the fields of space, sustainability, and climate.

HackTheBusiness Experience is more than just a competition – it's an immersive journey of learning and growth filled with business tricks and tips presented by the ENTREPRENEDU experts. Every participant had the invaluable opportunity to meet the panel of judges and mentors, receiving constructive feedback aimed at improving their ideas and strategies to perfection. Participants benefited from practical business tips and tricks, all designed to maximize their hacking efficiency. Furthermore, the esteemed panel of judges and mentors offered invaluable feedback, helping participants refine their ideas and strategies to a competitive edge.

HackTheBusiness fostered a collaborative environment that pushed boundaries and ignited new business ideas. With this successful foundation, ENTREPRENEDU paves the way for future hackathons to empower even more young minds across Europe.

ANNEX

PRESENTATION TEMPLATE

Instructions (1/3) – Using this Template

- This template provides some generic slides to give you inspiration and a general idea of what you could present.
- Make this template your own: add your own branding/personal touch, make use of the Slide Master (View tab → Slide Master).
- Keep your slides clean and attractive. A picture is worth a thousand words.
- The pitch deck is **not** supposed to be a standalone document: it should always be coupled with your speech. Don't overload it with too much text. If you have to reduce the fonts-size of your main text below 14-16, then you are doing it wrong!
- Feel free to make use of a back-up slides section to be prepared for the Q&A session.
- Do not include any Instructions slides upon in your final presentation.

1

Instructions (2/3) – Pitch-deck Approach

- The duration of the presentation will be **strictly** regulated (limit to be announced during the competition).
- The presentation should be complete.
- The presentation must respond to all the evaluation criteria.
- Presentations can be supported by real prototypes, slides and/or any other audiovisual media, if available.
- Teams should keep in mind that they are targeting a potential client/investor and want to persuade them to invest in their idea.

2

Instructions (3/3) – Judging Criteria

- **Technical Innovation:** Is the idea innovative? Does it rely on Technology Transfer? Does it have the potential to secure Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs)?
- **Market Attractiveness:** Does the idea address a real problem? Is there a market for it?
- **Business Viability:** Is the business model sound? Can a company build around the presented idea run a successful business?
- **Investors Interest:** Overall, can the idea attract interest from potential investors?
- **Funding Opportunities:** Does the idea have the potential to secure funding from other sources (beyond investors), such as grants?
- **Educational Impact:** Does the business/idea have a (side-)effect on the education sector? Can people be trained/educated through it?
- **Team Quality:** Is this the Team to solve the Problem?
- **Branding & Marketing:** Has the team worked on its values, its branding, and its marketing (e.g., name selection for business/product, logo creation, graphics, creative content, etc.).

3

Company or Project or Product Name

generic logo company
Generic motto

The problem / opportunity / concept

generic logo company

Manufacturers have embraced pilot projects that promise to lead to optimized costs and improved quality when scaled. The reality is that such projects lack scalability and never reach the full roll-out stage.

70% of manufacturing companies fail to escape the pilot purgatory*.

<p>30% IoT projects fail in POC, often because implementation is expensive, or the bottom-line benefits are unclear.</p>	<p>38% mention complexity and technical challenges as top barrier.</p>	<p>47% mention lack of talent and training as barrier to adoption.</p>
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*IoT-Signals-Microsoft-072019.pdf

The solution / product / service

generic logo company

ISML

Integrated Solution (Hardware & Software) powered by Machine Learning technologies.

Real-time monitoring, threats detection, and prediction.

Early warnings and preventive actions sent.

Decision making support through analysed data and visuals.

The solution / product / service

generic logo company

ISML processes data from various sources (sensors, cameras, etc.), for timely problem identification and immediate intervention.

Measurements Collection & pre-Processing

Processing & Data Analysis

Information Visualization

The market (total / accessible / growth)

TAM \$1T
SAM \$300B
SOM \$32B

800 companies Greek Target Market
 90,000 companies European Target Market
 4,000,000 companies USA & EU Market

The business / pricing model

ISML can be applied as a complete solution or as a supplementary solution to existing infrastructure.

There are 3 types of potential collaborations:

- Complete Solution (HW&SW)
- Data Analysis and Software applications (SW)
- Monitoring & Control Devices (HW)

Revenue = Installation fee + Support Fee (Recurring) + License Fees (Usage - Recurring)

The Unique Selling Point

Scalability: One solution for all applications.	Reliability: 100% in-house development	Support	Price
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The modular structure of the HW & SW allows scalability for any future digital need. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No dependency on third party products for data processing. Continuous operation based on the edge. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Immediate availability Remote technical support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low installation & maintenance cost Low scalability cost No hidden costs

The Competition

Traditional players are distinguished for their reliability, but are inflexible to change, offer limited applications, and their investment costs are prohibitive.

New players offer limited applications that require handling by technically qualified personnel.

The Competition #2

Customer-centric Features	Competitor 1	Competitor 1	Competitor 1	Competitor 1	Your Company
Feature 1	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Feature 2	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
Feature 3	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Feature 4	3/5	4/5	1/5	2/5	5/5
Feature 5	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
Price	\$\$	\$\$\$	\$	\$\$	\$

The Impact (Educational, Social, etc.)

The innovative solution introduced is bound to inspire a new generation of young engineers in our field.

Various scientific results are expected to be produced and made public in the academia under our R&D activities.

The team

Senior Management			Mentors / Advisors		
Rebeca Blue CEO Production & Management Engineer, MBA, MSc. 10 years in Business Development. Collaboration in R&D projects with NASA, ESA. Coordination of SO-H2020 R&D projects.	James Bond CTO Electrical & Computer Engineer, MSc. 40 years in IoT Product Development. Technical Manager in more than 1,000 R&D projects. Collaboration in projects with NASA, ESA, MSc.	Panagiotis Gika Head of Systems Engineering Electrical & Computer Engineer, MSc. 10 years in Embedded Software Development.	Eleni Petrou National Representative, USA. Business Advisor (25 years) Board Member of the National Council.	John Smith Technical Director, Hellenic Spaceforce (20 years). Production Director, Company Electronics S.A. (20 years).	Orfeas Voutyras Professor of Nuclear Physics at NTUA Athens. Scientific Delegate of Greece to the ICRN Council (2005-2017).

The implementation / time plan / milestones

Q3 2021: Feature Definition, Prototyping
 Q1 2022: Software Development, Patent Application
 Q2 2022: Patent Application
 Q3 2022: Strategic Partnerships, Preparation to enter market, Investment

The financials / investment / revenue / expenses

The Ask: To reach its goals until the end of 2022, the company needs **60k euros**.

Projections for the next 18 months

	2021	2022
REVENUE	€ 11,000.00	€ 11,000.00
COST OF GOODS	€ 1,000.00	€ 1,000.00
OPERATIONAL COSTS	€ 1,200.00	€ 1,200.00
GRANTS	€ 1,000.00	€ 1,000.00
EBITDA	€ 1,000.00	€ 1,000.00
DEPRECIATION	€ 1,000.00	€ 1,000.00
NET PROFIT	€ 1,000.00	€ 1,000.00
FREE CASH FLOW	€ 1,000.00	€ 1,000.00

17

Thank you for your attention!

42 Kifisias, 14564, Athens, GR
www.company.gr – sales@company.gr

AUTHORIZATION FORM

Authorisation Form

I, the undersigned _____

City of birth _____ Country _____ Date _____

Residential Address _____

City _____ Country _____ Zip _____ Code _____

I grant permission to use my image in photograph(s) and videos in any publications or publicity materials that will be taken at Kick-off meeting, General Assemblies, Steering Committees, regular project meetings, and to all and any other project events and meetings related to the development of the EU Funded project 101100507 — ENTREPRENEDU — HORIZON-EIE-2022-SCALEUP-01.

I HEREBY AUTHORIZE

At no charge, and in perpetuity, also in accordance with Articles 10 and 320 of the Italian Civil Code and Articles 96 and 97 of Law 22.4.1941, No. 633, Law on Copyright, to the publication and/or dissemination in any form of his/her images on websites, social networks, printed paper and/or any other means of dissemination, as well as authorize the preservation of the photos and videos themselves in the computer archives of the consortium partners and acknowledges that the purpose of such publications are purely informative and promotional. This release/authorization may be revoked at any time by written notice to be sent by common mail or e-mail to the consortium partners.

Policy for the publication of personal information

I also declare that I give my consent to the Processing of Personal Data in accordance with the EU Regulation 2016/679 and the Personal Data Protection Code (Legislative Decree 196/2003). Please note that the "European Regulation 2016/679 on the Protection of Individuals with regard to the Processing of Personal Data and on the free movement of such data" (henceforth GDPR) provides for the protection of persons and other subjects with regard to the processing of personal data. Within the limits pertinent to the processing purposes indicated, personal data may be subject to communication, publication and/or dissemination in any form on the website and any other means of dissemination (paper and telematic modes). The provision of consent to the processing of personal data referred to above is optional. At any time it is possible to exercise all the rights indicated in Articles 15 to 22 and Article 34 of the GDPR, in particular the cancellation, rectification or integration of data, with written communication to be sent to the Data Controller or the External Data Controller.

I give my consent
 I deny consent

Place and Date: _____ (Legible) Signature: _____

Project: 101100507 — ENTREPRENEDU — HORIZON-EIE-2022-SCALEUP-01 1

FIGURE 52 AUTHORIZATION FORM TEMPLATE

PRESS RELEASES

ENTREPRENEDU
Enhancing entrepreneurial ecosystems for education

GROUNDBREAKING IDEAS SHINE AT ENTREPRENEDU'S FIRST HACKTHEBUSINESS COMPETITION IN RIMINI, ITALY

Monday, 3rd of July 2023

Led by the mission to support young entrepreneurs in turning their ideas into successful businesses, ENTREPRENEDU project is organising a series of 3 business competitions named HackTheBusiness.

HackTheBusiness, an entrepreneurship challenge designed for young minds, empowers participants to learn, explore, and discover the secrets of the DeepTech industry. The competition encourages thinking outside the box, refining pitches, and harnessing creativity. Beyond a mere competition, HackTheBusiness also serves as an opportunity for collaboration, learning and growth, offering participants the chance to engage with ENTREPRENEDU mentors and receive constructive feedback from esteemed judges and industry leaders.

The first HackTheBusiness event took place from 15 to 17 of June at [We Make Future](#) in Rimini, Italy, and was aimed at 30 teams including students, new start-ups and researchers who want to acquire entrepreneurial skills and explore their business potential.

During the 3-day event, participants were presented with a challenge: to pitch groundbreaking problem-solving ideas in the fields of SpaceTech, ClimateTech, or FoodTech. They were then given 72 hours to refine their ideation concepts with the constant guidance of ENTREPRENEDU mentors.

The pitches were evaluated based on various criteria, including innovation, feasibility, market scalability, and social impact. At the end of the competition, ENTREPRENEDU's panel of experts selected the four winning teams and their innovative DeepTech ideas:

Winner #1: BACKWARDS

BACKWARDS team aims to tackle the issue of packaging waste by creating reusable packaging and logistics infrastructure.

Winner #2: SHADES OF BLUE

SHADES OF BLUE team aspires to establish a certification system and consultancy services for sustainable water resource management, helping companies monitor, improve, and communicate their impact on rivers and water.

Winner #3: AS YOU LIKE

AS YOU LIKE seeks to transform the dining experience through a mobile app that enables users to customise meals, access real-time nutrition information using Visual-AI, and discover restaurants aligned with their dietary needs.

FIGURE 53 EXTRACT FROM PRESS RELEASE, HACKTHEBUSINESS ITALY

HACKTHEBUSINESS HACKATHON BRINGS TOGETHER SPACE ENTREPRENEURS FOR A DAY IN GREECE

[Athens, 25.11.2023]

HackTheBusiness second edition has reunited young entrepreneurs and startups at Corallia (Athens, Greece) for a day, where they had the opportunity to pitch their innovative business idea and compete for a place in the Mentoring & Coaching Programme delivered by ENTREPRENEDU project.

[ENTREPRENEDU](#), an innovative EU funded initiative fostering entrepreneurial spirit of young European professionals, proudly announced a triumphant culmination of its recent event, [HackTheBusiness Greece](#). The event was a resounding success, bringing together bright minds to ignite space innovation and entrepreneurship in Greece. “The objective of ENTREPRENEDU is ambitious and it represents a unique opportunity for the European innovation ecosystem to have a replicable and scalable model to support education of young professionals. HackTheBusiness is the first milestone to reach this pioneering goal”, explains [Valerio Roscani](#), [ENTREPRENEDU](#) Project Manager and Technology Analyst at [Fondazione E. Amaldi](#).

FIGURE 54 EXTRACT FROM PRESS RELEASE, HACKTHEBUSSINESS GREECE

ENTREPRENEDU PROJECT ASSEMBLED SUSTAINABILITY INNOVATORS IN SOFIA, BULGARIA FOR THE FINAL HACKTHEBUSINESS EVENT

[Sofia, 29.03.2024.]

On the 26th and 27th of March 2024, young entrepreneurs, researchers and early-stage startups gathered at the final HackTheBusiness competition, at Innovation Forum “John Atanasoff” at Sofia Tech Park (Sofia, Bulgaria), to pitch their innovative and sustainable business idea and compete for a place in the Mentoring & Coaching Programme delivered by [ENTREPRENEDU project](#).

Hosted by [CleanTech Bulgaria](#), the final in the series of three HackTheBusiness hackathons ignited the spark of innovation, transforming the future of the European sustainable ecosystem through green and eco-conscious solutions related to agri-food, construction, manufacturing and digital and creative industries. HackTheBusiness Bulgaria participants were encouraged to think creatively when addressing environmental concerns, with a goal to contribute to a more eco-conscious and resilient future in these key sectors. Additionally, networking opportunities were made possible by the event, allowing all attendees to create lasting relationships that go beyond the occasion. Ina Todorova, [HackTheBusiness Bulgaria](#)

FIGURE 55 EXTRACT FROM PRESS RELEASE, HACKTHEBUSSINESS BULGARIA

REGISTRATION FORMS

155 Pipeline Scouting Apply Events Jobs Deals

Add your Search

Edit Cover

HackTheBusiness | Italy
Hackathon

Anja & Daniel + 2

DISCUSS

You know 1 connection

Jun 15-17 '23 (3 days)

Via Emilia, Rimini Expo Centre
Rimini, Italy

HackTheBusiness - Italy
Hackathon topic: DeepTech

Hackathon challenges:
- Space
- Food
- Climate

Your Answers @
Ticket - General Admission

- 1 First Name
- 2 Last Name
- 3 Country
- 4 Age
- 5 Gender
- 6 Email address
- 7 Phone number
- 8 What is your background?
Information and Communication Technologies

FIGURE 56 HACKTHEBUSINESS ITALY - EXTRACT OF THE REGISTRATION FORM

155 Pipeline Scouting Apply Events Jobs Deals

Add your Search

Edit Cover

HackTheBusiness | Greece
Hackathon

Anja & Daniel + 3

DISCUSS

You know 1 connection

Jun 15-17 '23 (3 days)

Add Street address
Athens, Greece

HackTheBusiness - Greece - Space technologies

Dates:
1st phase: 03-05 November 2023 (5 different locations)
2nd phase: 25 November 2023 (Athens, Greece)

About the competition:

Your Answers @
Ticket - General Admission

- 1 First Name
- 2 Last Name
- 3 Nationality
- 4 Country of residence
- 5 Age
- 6 Gender
- 7 Email address
- 8 Phone number
- 9 Local events (03-05 November 2023)

FIGURE 57 HACKTHEBUSINESS GREECE - EXTRACT OF THE REGISTRATION FORM

FIGURE 58 HACKTHEBUSINESS BULGARIA - EXTRACT OF THE REGISTRATION FORM